

Rabbits were immunized against RTSV by 4 intramuscular and 1 intraveinal injections at 2-wk intervals with purified virus (A_{260} adjusted to 1.0 mixed with equal volume of Freund's complete adjuvant). An antiserum with a titer of 1:640 in ring interface precipitin and 1:160 in double gel diffusion (Ouchterlony) tests was obtained. An Ouchterlony test was used to compare RTSV and RWV antisera. A single band formed between homologous and heterologous combinations and the reaction bands fused (Fig. 2). Hence, RTSV is not only morphologically similar but also serologically identical to RWV. □

1. Electron micrograph of purified RTSV negatively stained with 2% phosphotungstic acid (200,000X), IRRI.

2. Ouchterlony test showing serological relation between RTSV and RWV: the center well contains purified RTSV and outer wells contain antiserum to RWV (W), antiserum to RTSV (S), and phosphate buffer (b), IRRI.

An alternative host for *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Tak.

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Rice false smut, also known as pseudosmut or green smut, caused by *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Tak. was first reported by Cooke (1878) from Tinnevely in Tamil Nadu, India. The disease cycle of the pathogen is still obscure.

During an extensive survey of false smut incidence in Dakshina Kannada District in 1983 kharif, we found that

Digitaria marginata L., a common rice weed, also was infected with false smut in 85% of the fields surveyed.

We conducted a cross-inoculation test to determine the infectivity to rice panicles of smut spores occurring on *D. marginata*. Smut balls (pseudomorphs) were collected from infected *D. marginata* and a spore suspension (about 10^4 spores/ml) was prepared in sterile distilled water. The suspension was inoculated on individual Basmati spikelets. The inoculated panicles were covered with polyethylene bags for 15 d and observed for smut ball development.

Ten days after inoculation, yellowish

smut balls began to emerge from the glumes. About half of the inoculated florets developed into smut balls.

We found *D. marginata* around the field was infected with false smut before panicle-bearing rice tillers matured. It is possible that when rice flowers open, the smut spores from infected *D. marginata* become airborne and infect them. Either chlamyospores from hibernating pseudomorphs or ascospores from germinated sclerotia may act as primary inoculum for infecting *D. marginata*. From *D. marginata* the smut spores cross-infect rice. □

Rice yellow dwarf in Tamil Nadu, India

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Yellow dwarf infected a large area of rice in Pudukkottai District of Tamil Nadu in Aug 1984. Of 1,000 ha surveyed, more than 200 ha in rice at different growth stages was affected. In each infected field, 1 m² was randomly selected, total and infected hills were counted, and percent disease was calculated. ADT36, TKM9, IR20, and IR50 were susceptible (see table). Maximum infection was 40% on IR20. Co 33 had 7% infection. Green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* popula-

Incidence of yellow dwarf in rice varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.

Village surveyed	Variety	Infection (%)
Satharam	ADT36	12.6
Kamathipuram	ADT36	24.1
Arimalam	ADT36	10.0
Kamarajapuram	ADT36	18.8
Mirattunilai	ADT36	16.6
Mirattunilai	ADT36	12.5
	IR20	39.6
	IR20	21.8
	IR20	14.2
	IR20	23.1
Meenakshipuram	TKM9	15.9
	IR50	10.0
Kalyanapuram	Co 33	1.5

tion was high. Although some disease had been noticed in previous years, this was the first widespread occurrence. □

Development of rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) in the vector brown planthopper (BPH)

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We studied RSV development in BPH. Virus-free BPH 1st and 3d-instar nymphs were allowed to feed separately on RSV-infected plants for 4 d and then held on healthy TN1 seedlings. Insects were collected every 2 d and homogenized with 0.2 M phosphate buffered-saline (pH 6.5) containing 0.05% Tween plus 2% polyvinylpyrrolidone at 0.05 ml/insect and 0.1 ml/insect for 1st and 3d instars. Extracts were tested for RSV antigen in ELISA using polystyrene microtitre plates (immulon). The relative content